

EM Scattering by Electrically Large Inhomogeneous Dielectric Objects - MOM/Power Series Solution Approach

Sadasiva M. Rao
 Radar Division
 Naval Research Laboratory
 Washington DC 20375 (USA)

Abstract—In this work, we extend the recently developed method of moments/power series solution (MOM-PS) procedure to obtain radar cross section (RCS) of an inhomogeneous dielectric body due to a plane wave incidence. The procedure involves modeling the body using tetrahedron cells, assigning material parameters to each cell and employing Schaubert-Wilton-Glisson (SWG) functions to approximate the unknown flux density induced in the body. Next, we apply the recently developed MOM-PS procedure to solve for the unknowns. The new procedure is simple and yields accurate results for the material body problem.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, Killian et al. [1], and Rao [2] have presented a method to obtain the radar cross section (RCS) by electrically large, perfectly conducting (PEC) body via method of moments (MOM). In this work, we extend the method to obtain the RCS of an inhomogeneous dielectric body.

In brief, the procedure begins by approximating the inhomogeneous body via tetrahedral volume cells and representing the induced flux density distribution by Schaubert-Wilton-Glisson (SWG) functions. Next, the procedure involves renumbering the basis functions using a distance criterion and dividing the total number of basis functions into groups of equal size casting the moment matrix into a collection of submatrices representing self and mutual interaction between the groups. Next, the procedure requires eliminating the interaction of two immediate neighbors on any selected group. This process results in a strong block diagonal moment matrix plus zeros in the blocks residing on either side of the diagonal block. The new matrix can be approximately inverted using power series approach and accurate solution can be efficiently obtained. The present approach is simple, efficient, and retains all the advantages of conventional method of moments scheme.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Let V denote the volume of an inhomogeneous material body with complex dielectric constant $\hat{\epsilon}$ subjected to a plane wave incidence. The induced polarization current \mathbf{J} is related to incident and scattered fields by

$$\mathbf{J} = j\omega(\hat{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0)[\mathbf{E}^i + \mathbf{E}^s], \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{E}^i and \mathbf{E}^s represent the incident and scattered electric fields, respectively. Also, ω and ϵ_0 represent the angular

frequency of the incident wave and the permittivity of the surrounding medium, respectively. Further, the magnetic vector potential \mathbf{A} , and the electric scalar potential Φ are given by

$$\mathbf{A} = \mu_0 \int_V \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}') G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') dv', \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \int_V \rho(\mathbf{r}') G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') dv', \quad (3)$$

and

$$G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \frac{e^{-jk_0|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|}}{4\pi|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|}. \quad (4)$$

where $k_0 = \omega \sqrt{\mu_0 \epsilon_0}$ and μ_0 represents the permeability of the surrounding medium. In Eqs. (2) - (4), \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{r}' represent the position vectors to observation and source points with respect to a global coordinate origin \mathbf{O} . The charge density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ is related to the polarization current density by

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = -j\omega\rho(\mathbf{r}). \quad (5)$$

Eq. (1) along with Eqs. (2-5) constitute the necessary integro-differential equation to be solved using the conventional MOM procedure as described in [3].

III. MOM-PS SOLUTION PROCEDURE

To begin the numerical procedure, we order the basis functions using a distance criterion measured from a reference point, either from one end of the scatterer or from a convenient point on the scatterer. Using basis functions also as testing functions and using the standard method of moments procedure, the operator equation can be transformed into a matrix equation, given by

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{Y}. \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{Z} is a $N \times N$ matrix and \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} are the unknown and known column vectors of dimension N , respectively, and N represents the total number of basis functions.

Let us divide the N basis functions into P groups, with $M = N/P$ elements in each group. The \mathbf{Z} -matrix may be

written as

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{11} & \mathbf{Z}_{12} & \mathbf{Z}_{13} & \mathbf{Z}_{14} & \cdots & \mathbf{Z}_{1P} \\ \mathbf{Z}_{21} & \mathbf{Z}_{22} & \mathbf{Z}_{23} & \mathbf{Z}_{24} & \cdots & \mathbf{Z}_{2P} \\ \mathbf{Z}_{31} & \mathbf{Z}_{32} & \mathbf{Z}_{33} & \mathbf{Z}_{34} & \cdots & \mathbf{Z}_{3P} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{Z}_{P1} & \mathbf{Z}_{P2} & \mathbf{Z}_{P3} & \mathbf{Z}_{P4} & \cdots & \mathbf{Z}_{PP} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where each $\mathbf{Z}_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, P, j = 1, 2, \dots, P$ represents a submatrix of $M \times M$. In a similar manner, we can express the column vector \mathbf{Y} as

$$\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{Y}_1, \mathbf{Y}_2, \mathbf{Y}_3, \mathbf{Y}_4, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_P]^T \quad (8)$$

where the superscript ‘‘T’’ represents the transpose.

Next, we transform Eq. (6) to

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}\mathbf{X} = \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}. \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}} = \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{Z}, \tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{Y}$,

$$\mathbf{R}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{R}_{12} & \mathbf{R}_{13} & \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset \\ \emptyset & \mathbf{I} & \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset \\ \emptyset & \emptyset & \mathbf{I} & \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset & \cdots & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

\mathbf{R}_{12} and \mathbf{R}_{13} are $M \times M$ matrices with unknown coefficients, and \mathbf{I} and \emptyset are $M \times M$ identity and null matrices, respectively.

Considering the first row of the $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}$ -matrix, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{11} &= \mathbf{Z}_{11} + \mathbf{R}_{12}\mathbf{Z}_{21} + \mathbf{R}_{13}\mathbf{Z}_{31} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{12} &= \mathbf{Z}_{12} + \mathbf{R}_{12}\mathbf{Z}_{22} + \mathbf{R}_{13}\mathbf{Z}_{32} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{13} &= \mathbf{Z}_{13} + \mathbf{R}_{12}\mathbf{Z}_{23} + \mathbf{R}_{13}\mathbf{Z}_{33} \\ &\vdots \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{1P} &= \mathbf{Z}_{1P} + \mathbf{R}_{12}\mathbf{Z}_{2P} + \mathbf{R}_{13}\mathbf{Z}_{3P} \end{aligned}$$

Next, we solve for \mathbf{R}_{12} and \mathbf{R}_{13} by forcing the elements of $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{12}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{13}$ to zero. Thus, we solve

$$\mathbf{Z}_{12} + \mathbf{R}_{12}\mathbf{Z}_{22} + \mathbf{R}_{13}\mathbf{Z}_{32} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_{13} + \mathbf{R}_{12}\mathbf{Z}_{23} + \mathbf{R}_{13}\mathbf{Z}_{33} = 0 \quad (12)$$

simultaneously, which results in a solution of $2M \times 2M$ matrix with M right hand sides. Once, \mathbf{R}_{12} and \mathbf{R}_{13} are known, it is trivial to obtain $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}$.

By following a similar procedure to rows 2, 3, \dots, P and each time solving a $2M \times 2M$ matrix, we can generate a new matrix equation, given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{Z}}\mathbf{X} = \bar{\mathbf{Y}}. \quad (13)$$

where the new $\bar{\mathbf{Z}}$ -matrix is a block-wise diagonally-dominant matrix with zero blocks on either side of the diagonal block as described in [2]. Next, we solve the Eq. (13) by the power series method presented in [2].

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We consider two examples *viz.* a) dielectric sphere ($\epsilon_r = 2$) and b) a dielectric square cylinder ($\epsilon_r = 4$). The unknown volume current distribution is approximated by 4,910 and 6,430 basis functions for sphere and cylinder problems, respectively. We note a reasonably good comparison between the conventional MOM and the present method with only two terms in the power series.

Fig. 1. RCS of a dielectric sphere, radius $a = 0.4\lambda$, $\epsilon_r = 2$, illuminated by a x -polarized, z -traveling plane wave. Number of unknowns=4909, Number of groups=10.

Fig. 2. RCS of a three-dimensional square dielectric cylinder, $L = 5\lambda$ and $W = 0.2\lambda$, $\epsilon_r = 4$ placed along the z -axis illuminated by a z -polarized, x -traveling plane wave. Number of unknowns=6430, Number of groups=10.

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